

The Factors Affect Work-Life Balance for Lecturers: The Study at the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically investigates the level of adoption of work-life balance practices among lecturers working in higher education institutions in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. These factors include work-life conflict and work-life enrichment. We find that work-life conflict is not significantly associated with work-life balance. We also find that coping strategies that incorporate environmental and individual characteristics are perceived to alternatively help individuals attain work-life balance staff working in higher education institutions in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Moreover, work-life balance is positively associated with outcomes in both work and life dimensions. The findings of this study shed more light on the current work-life balance practices in the higher education institutions sector of Vietnam. Further research is required to understand the link between work-life balance and job satisfaction. This study identifies the factors which affect on work-life balance to help lecturers to reduce pressure in life-work, in order for lecturers to achieve personal goals and organizational goals.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Work-Life Balance (WLB) concept has become a subject of debate among scholars in recent decades. Since then, health, spirit, and life, as well as work quality, have deteriorated. Despite the fact that the issue of WLB is personal and concerns the lecturer's sentiments, its effects have a direct impact on the university. Work, family, relationships, and obstacles are all issues that workers must deal with on a daily basis and come up with solutions to. As a result, we sometimes give up, as if we have forgotten ourselves, that life requires rest periods, times when we may live for ourselves.

Although the definitions and concepts related to work life balance are varied. For example, Carlson et al. (2006) show that WLB can be understand as balance, harmony and the result of conflict between work and family or enrichment between work and home. This view is supported by Greenhaus et al. (2003), Carlson et al. (2009). Furthermore, Kalliath & Brough (2008) indicate that WLB can be seen in six different dimensions such as the individual's orientation role, the engagement in work and family role, the individual's effectiveness and satisfaction in work and family roles, the conflict and facilitation in work and life roles, and a measure of control over when, where and how they work. Thus, we can conclusion that WLB as a multiple constructs concept consisting of work and life conflict and enhancement in both directions, is an important notion as it captures more of the phenomenon.

This research will develop a model of WLB and identify specific elements that influence it. The findings of the study will serve as a foundation for future research and organizations seeking WLB solutions for lecturer in high education in University. With the above reasons, the author introduces the article about "THE FACTORS AFFECT WORK-LIFE BALANCE FOR LECTURER: THE STUDY AT THE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS HO CHI MINH CITY".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Basic theory for WLB

WLB is widely documented in both theoretical and conceptual implications perspective. From the theoretical perspective, WLB can be consider as the way to generate a healthy equilibrium between individual life and job tasks (Lingard et al., 2009). This

is supported by Greenhaus et al. (2003) who show that WLB is balance as a situation when lecturers can achieve the right balance between work and personal responsibilities. On the other hand, Zheng et al. (2015) define WLB as a fit between the demands of multiple roles and the availability of personal resources. WLB can be considering as a balance, harmony and outcome of work-family conflict or work-family enrichment (Clark, 2001).

In research, the term "work-life balance" is employed, which refers to more than only family and life. Work life, family life, social life, and private life are all referred to as "life" in this study. WLB can be understood as balance, harmony, and the result of work-family conflict (WLC), according to Carlson et al., (2009), as well as the reciprocal support between work and family (WLE). Furthermore, in a research titled "Work-life balance: A review of the meaning of the balance construct," Kalliath and Brough (2008) identified five main characteristics that might be addressed in the idea of life balance: (1) As a concept that reflects personal orientation in various life roles; (2) The extent to which an individual participates in both the work and family roles and is equally satisfied in both; (3) Achieving a satisfying experience in all areas of life by skillfully distributing personal resources such as energy, time, and other resources across all areas; (4) An individual's level of effectiveness and satisfaction in work and family roles corresponds to the individual's priorities at a given time; (5) It's about people who have a measure of control over when, where, and how they work. Therefore, it can be understood that WLB is a multi-structural concept that includes WLC and WLE.

Lecturers at the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City: The faculty of Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics (UEH) is a team of highly qualified professionals, with many professors, associate professors, doctors and masters, playing an important role in training in economics and business in Vietnam. Data for the 2022-2023 academic year shows that there are 627 permanent lecturers, including 11 professors, 64 associate professors, 261 doctors and 289 masters. Duties and positions, the functions, rights and interests of service workers are clearly defined in: (1) *Regulations on organization and operation*; (2) *Functions and duties of the units*; (3) *Regulations on internal spending*. The lecturers have three functions: (1) Teaching; (2) Scientific research; (3) serve the community.

2.2. Factors affecting WLB for lecturers at the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City

WLB is widely study documented in both theoretical and practical sense. From a theoretical point of view, WLB can be seen as a way to create a healthy balance for personal life and work tasks (Lingard et al., 2009). WLB, on the other hand, is defined by Zheng et al. (2015) as the fit between the needs of multiple roles and the availability of individual resources. WLB can be seen as a balance, harmony and result of work-family conflict or work-family enrichment (Clark, 2004). As a result, we can anticipate that two significant factors can influence WLB: work-life conflict and work-life enrichment. In view of the relationship between WLB and job performance (OUT), previous research has shown that higher WLB levels can contribute to higher quality of life and job satisfaction, increase job satisfaction, as well as reduce employee turnover (Bradley et al., 2010; Brough et al., 2014). This relationship has also been extensively investigated from previous studies across different disciplines (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007; Rantanen et al., 2010). As a result, we consider this link in our study utilizing a sample of UEH-UD service workers.

Through theoretical research and empirical studies from many sources, authors and a combination of qualitative research methods (expert interview method) thereby identifying groups of factors that help WLB for lecturers to recover. service at UEH. Expert interview methods will be introduced in the study design chapter). The purpose of this research model is to examine the level of implementation of WLB methods for service workers at UEH. The following are the research objectives presented in this study: (1) Explore a theoretical framework underpinning the interpretation and clarification of WLB; (2) Predict and evaluate WLB based on service workers' perceptions through investigation and interpretation of results during the evaluation process. In summary, the goal of this research is to operationalize the WLB concept and to put the conceptual framework to the test by conducting empirical studies in practice. WLB can be viewed as a means of striking a balance between personal and professional life (Lingard et al., 2009). Greenhaus et al. (2003) have also shown that WLB is achieved when lecturers are able to strike the right balance between work and personal responsibilities. On the other hand, Zheng et al., (2015) define WLB as the match between the needs and availability of individual resources. WLB can also be viewed as a balance, harmony and result of work-life conflict and work-life enrichment (Clark, 2004). Therefore, from a WLB perspective, WLB can be influenced by WLC and WLE.

Given the link between WLB and Outcomes of Work–Life Balance (OUT), prior research have shown that high WLB levels can improve quality of life and job satisfaction while also reducing change and employee turnover (Greenhaus et al., 2003; Bradley et al., 2010; Brough et al., 2014). This relationship has been studied extensively in previous studies (Grzywacz and Carlson, 2007; Rantanen et al., 2010). Therefore, the following sections present an analysis of the main components of the WLB model in the context of WLC, WLE, as well as OUT.

Greenhaus & Beutell (1985) show that WLC is "a form of inter-role conflict in which role pressures from work and family domains are mutually incompatible". According to Carlson et al. (2009), WLC is a critical source of stress in our life. They also mention that the level of WLC is dependent on the work demand (WD) and life demand (LD). In other word, the level of WLC is driven by the bidirectional in nature and produce negative effects from one domain to another. This is consistent with the findings of Michel et al. (2010). Furthermore, from the spirits of the Greenhaus & Beutell (1985) and Carlson et al. (2000) research results on the structure of WLC, in this study, we can measure WLC base on three dimensions: time-based conflict, strain-based conflict and behavior-based conflict.

In the next section, we move to the concept of WLE. Preliminary work on WLE was undertaken by Carlson et al. (2006). They indicate that WLE is the positive side of the relationship between work and life domains. They also argue that WLE will provide the resources to help them increase the level of satisfaction in the life domain. Following Carlson et al. (2006) and Mcmillan et al. (2010), in this study, WLE can be captured by four types of resources such as developmental, efficiency, affective and capital gains.

A considerable amount of literature has been published on WLC and WLE relative to the WLB concepts. The result from demands and resources would directly affect WLB through the appraisal of WLC and WLE. Detailed examination of WLC, WLE and WLB by Frone (2003) and Haddon & Hede (2010) showed that low level of WLC and high level of WLE leads to WLB. The level of WLC is positively associated with an individual's ability to meet the demands whereas the level of WLE is positively associated with the amount of resources that an individual possesses to meet the demands and personal performance (Haddon et al., 2009; Haddon & Hede, 2010).

Based on the hypotheses presented below, WLE and WLC are positively associated with resources and demands respectively. An individual may engage in strategies that can help alter the outcome of WLC or WLE in order to achieve WLB. This led to the formulation of the following hypotheses. WLB is considered to be a set of more measurable structures than a unidimensional construct (Rantanen et al., 2010). In order to interpret an individual's WLB structure, the previous study reveals that WLC and WLE are considered two important indicators acting as linkage mechanisms to interpret WLB (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007). Furthermore, it has been observed that high WLE and/or low WLC lead to the attainment of WLB (Frone, 2003). In addition to WLC and WLE, which link to WLB, the CS has been identified as the third way for an individual to achieve WLB. It means that WLE, WLC, and CS are critical domains to in interpreting WLB concept. This led to the formulation of the following hypotheses, see Fig. 1:

Fig. 1: Proposed research model

- Hypothesis H1: WLC is negatively correlated with WLB.
- Hypothesis H2: WLE is positively correlated with WLB.

WLB and OUT: It is important to investigate the WLB results to understand the benefits or adverse effects of the balance (imbalance) in work and life relation. Carlson et al. (2009) show that WLB contributes to the interpretation of both work and life results. In terms of performance, WLB is designed to improve job satisfaction, organizational commitment and enterprise change intentions (Carlson et al., 2000; Carlson et al., 2009). In terms of life outcomes, WLB is designed to improve life satisfaction, family satisfaction and psychological health (Carlson et al., 2006). Thus, this leads to the following hypothesis:

- Hypothesis H3: WLB is positively correlated with OUT.

The following table presents the sub-indicators, theoretical sources and measured item sources. All variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Question and Hypothesis: The objective of this study is to answer the question of how WLB is described and measured for service workers. We utilized the following fundamental approaches to create the above-mentioned suggested model: Synthetic material method, expert interview method. The first method, we synthesized scientific articles from many prestigious journals related to WLB assessment from 1986 to 2018. Through this method, we can introduce potential factors that have been used in previous studies, thereby forming an evaluation model. The second method, we use expert interview method. We must pick interviewers who are specialists in the field of human resource management for this method. We chose 25 people with whom to conduct interviews. To conduct interviews, we compiled a list of potential interviewees from a variety of organizations working in a variety of disciplines. The duration of the interviews ranged from 55 minutes to 1 hour. After completing the interview, we synthesize the above criteria as well as other factors. Through these steps, we can adjust, add, and remove duplicate, non-representative variables, thereby building a better model with higher reliability, more suitable for specific research conditions.

The sample is lecturers in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Participants are selected through the authors'

networks: friends, family members, colleagues, and university alumni. To ensure the representativeness of the sample, participants were recruited in universities and campus, institute and center. We posit that the lecturers in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City would provide an indication of the higher level of WLB demands and resources issues. Of the 160 questionnaires sent, the study will introduce the content related to testing the proposed theoretical model through two-step approach in building a linear structural model (SEM) (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Hair et al., 2010). Using AMOS software, a covariance-based SEM method (CB-SEM) was used. CB-SEM is used to verify (or refute) the model's validity (measurement and structure), assumptions, variable correlations, statistical significance, and grouping of similarity variables. There are two main steps: the first is to assess the validity of the suggested measurement model, and the second is to assess the structural model's validity. SPSS V.20 and AMOS V.20. were used to analyze the data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Validity and reliability evaluation

To evaluate the accuracy of the scales in the research model, the study will calculate the accuracy value following each individual scale and be evaluated by analyzing the convergence or divergence of the scales, and overall fit.

First, the reliability of the factors is measured to ensure that the observed variables in the same factor are related to each other. Statistically, two basic reliability metrics are used: the item-total correlation and the Cronbach's alpha, which the item-total correlation must be greater than 0.05, while the Cronbach's alpha must be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al, 2010). Summarizes the final results:

Table 2. Summary of the path coefficient, t-value and p values

Factors	Observed variables	The item-total correlation (>0.05)	The Cronbach's alpha (>0.7)	AVE (>0.05)
Work-life conflict (WLC)	WLC1	0.725	0.732	0.505
	WLC2	0.801		
	WLC3	0.701		
Work-life Enrichment (WLE)	WLE1	0.899	0.845	0.868
	WLE2	0.745		
	WLE3	0.801		
	WLE4	0.876		
Work-life balance	WLB1	0.799	0.812	0.730
	WLB2	0.896		
Work-life Outcomes (OUT)	OUT1	0.752	0.933	0.719
	OUT2	0.898		
	OUT3	0.901		

Note: * The bolded part is the group of factos consist of: WLB is work-life balance; WLC is work-life conflict; WLE is work-life enrichment; OUT is the work-life outcomes.

Table 2 summarizes the research findings, which demonstrate that all of the observed variables achieve the convergent value in each factor. Furthermore, Composite Reliability (CR) are higher than the 0.7 criterion (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). The AVE value of the constructs exceeded 0.5 (Hair et al., 2010). As a consequence of the findings, we may deduce that all observed variables are reliable and have appropriate convergence values.

Discriminant validity shows the differences in correlation between different factors. A high discriminant validity that the measured factor is unique and that the observed variables can generalize about the content contained in that factor. In this study, based on the results in Table 3, the discriminant validity for all observed variables is satisfactory, because the square root of the AVE values for the two constructs is larger than the item-total correlation (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 3. Square root value of AVE and correlation between factors

	WLC	WLE	WLB	OUT
WLC	0.812			
WLE	-0.405	0.833		
WLB	-0.391	0.278	0.854	
OUT	-0.575	0.237	0.533	0.844

*Note: * The bolded part is the square root value of AVE; WLB is work-life balance; WLC is work-life conflict; WLE is work-life enrichment; OUT is the work-life outcomes.*

Essentially, the Goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric indicates which model reflects the theory that best represents the data. Evaluation of model fit is one of the most important steps in the analysis of a linear structural model (Yuan, 2006). The statistics showing the Goodness-of-fit of the model are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Statistical value of model fit

Model fit	
CMIN = 252.84	CFI = 0.914
Df = 138	RMSEA = 0.052
CMIN/df = 1.83	PCLOSE = 0.365
p-value = 0.00	

Statistical indicators show the fit of the research model. The CMIN/df index of 1.83 is almost at the value of 2. The RMSEA at 0.05 is well below the upper limit of 0.07 and the PCLOSE at 0.365 is much larger than the threshold of 0.07 (Steiger, 2007). RMSEA at 0.052, satisfactory level. The CFI at 0.914 is higher than 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999).

4.2. Structural model evaluation

After the validity and reliability of the measurement model were established, the structural model was addressed. The structural model was used to determine the model’s capabilities in predicting the relationships between the constructs as well as to test the hypotheses formulated for the research. the significance and relevancy of the structural model relationships were assessed based on Path Coefficient and t-statistics. To evaluate the path coefficients, the PLS-SEM algorithms are used and the results are presented in **Table 5**. To next assess whether all the relationships between constructs were significant, the Bootstrapping interface was run. Bootstrapping is a nonparametric procedure where subsamples are randomly and automatically drawn from the data. This allows testing of the statistical significance of the path coefficients (Hair et al., 2017). When using the Bootstrapping interface, one has to note that the results of the t-statistics or other data would be different as it uses different subsamples for generating results.

Table 5. Hypothesis Test of model

Hypothesis	Coefficient	Effect	P value (<0.05)	Accept
H1: WLC negative correlation WLB	-0.38	-	0.00	Yes
H2: WLE positive correlation WLB	0.17	+	0.00	Yes
H3: WLB positive correlation OUT	0.20	+	0.00	Yes

As we can see that, at the 5% significance level, it could be seen that all the relationships in the structural model were significant Based on the result, only H1, H2, H3 are accepted as the t-value is significant at p<0.05. Increasing WLE or reducing WLC were significant in explaining WLB.

The next evaluation of the effect size of f² was the next step in assessing the structural model. The results of the f² effect size is presented in **Table 6**. Hair et al. (2017) indicated that the f² values is as follows: 0.02 = small effects; 0.15 = medium effects; 0.38 = large effects; less than 0.02 = no effect.

Table 6. Summary of f² effect size

	OUT	WLB	WLC	WLE
OUT		0.399		
WLB	0.501			
WLC		0.033		
WLE	0,612	0.001		

From the **Table 6** results, we can conclusion that: WLB has large effect on OUT (0.612); WLE has no effect on WLB (0.001); WLE has large effect on OUT (0.501); WLC has small effect on WLB (0.033), OUT has large effect on WLB (0.399).

Next, we evaluate the predictive relevance of Q^2 value by using the Blindfolding interface (Hair et al., 2017). The Construct Cross-validated Redundancy estimates are presented in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Summary of Q^2 value

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2=(1-SSE/SSO)$
OUT	156.00	128.12	0.153
WLB	52.00	35.99	0.189
WLC	173.00	125.72	0.270
WLE	175.00	117.35	0.315

It could be seen that all five endogenous constructs have Q^2 value above zero (Outcome = 0.153, WLB = 0.189, WLC = 0.270 and WLE = 0.315). The results clearly supported the model’s predictive relevancy regarding the endogenous latent variables.

The final step in evaluating the structural mode, the effect size of q^2 is used to evaluate where it assessed an exogenous latent variable’s contribution to an endogenous construct’s Q^2 value (Hair et al., 2017). The results are presented in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Summary of the $Q^2_{excluded}$ and q^2 effect size

	$Q^2_{excluded}$	$Q^2_{included}$	q^2	Predictive relevance
WLC → WLB	0.387	0.3311	-0.078	Small
WLE → OUT	-0.052	0.2645	0.301	Large
WLE → WLB	0.32	0.2145	-0.052	Small

Following Hair et al. (2017) method, we can conclusion that the q^2 effect size for all the relationship between variables could be considered as small predictive relevance, except WLE → OUT. In other word, this result implies that there is a small effect on the change in the R^2 value after the omission of one of its linked exogenous constructs. We also can see that the the q^2 effect size for the relationship between WLE → OUT could be considered as close to large predictive relevance.

4.3. Discussion

This study shows that WLC and WLE both have an impact on the level of WLB, and WLB has a positive impact on work outcomes. Overall, the theoretical model developed in this study explained 25% of the variance in work-life balance.

Fig. 2: Evaluation results according to the linear structural model

Structural analysis indicated that WLE and WLB had a positive association, in contrast, WLC had a negative association with WLB. As shown in Figure 2, we can see that the better the reciprocal support between work and life, the higher the level of work outcome of those working in lecturers at the University. The findings of this study are similar to those of earlier studies such

as Frone's (2003). As a consequence of the findings, we can conclude that the degree of work-life balance in the service sector at the school may be measured using two basic elements, WLE and WLC, as indicated in the model. Work-life balance also has an impact on work outcomes.

Thus, the research results show that WLC has an inverse relationship with WLB (beta coefficient = -0.45, $p = 0.00$). Therefore, hypothesis H1 was supported. The results support the model developed by Voydanoff (2005a) and Carlson et al. (2000) in which Work-life conflict is an assessment based on the perception of the impact of Work-life conflict.

Lecturers' work conflict has grown considerably as a result of their expanded job duties as a result of their high-level classification. "Work is always the major cause of troubles, no matter how beautiful your life is" according to one lecturer. Without a doubt, the work demands bring work and life into conflict. Thus, lecturers find that in work demands are more likely to cause work-life conflict and reduce work-life balance.

Hypothesis H3 suggests that there is a positive relationship between WLB and OUT. From the research results, hypothesis H3 is positive and significant (beta = 0.25, $p = 0.00$). Therefore, hypothesis H3 was supported. This significant result is consistent with many previous studies: WLB will yield positive results in WLB (Carlson et al., 2009; Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007; Haddon & Hede, 2010).

5. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to assess the level of WLB for lecturers in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. To achieve the research objective, the study first reviewed related theories and developed a conceptual framework that can estimate the WLB level. The results of this study have academic and practical value. First, this study estimates the observed variables that measure WLC and WLE, which are two basic aspects in measuring WLB. Second, the study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between WLC and WLE on WLB for lecturers in the University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Finally, research reveals that WLB and OUT have significant positive relationship. This means that greater WLB levels are linked to increased job and life satisfaction, as well as improved work performance.

The outcomes of this study have major significance for companies and managers from a practical implications' perspective. In addition, the findings of this study can assist managers in implementing effective and strategic policies and procedures to promote WLB inside their organizations. The findings also suggest that WLC has a greater effect on WLB than WLE. This means that limiting conflicts in work-life relationships is also a way to increase WLB levels.

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